

Understanding the Theoretical Relationship between Service Quality & Tourist Satisfaction: Special Reference to Tourism Industry

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Abstract

There is widespread exposure in the literature of tourist satisfaction and service quality in a tourist destination. Many service related industry gives due weight age to service because it contribute a lot in business growth. Competition is increasing tourism industry at very fast pace. Excellent service quality offers to customers results in increase level of satisfaction and revisit of customers and increase profit of the company. Tourist satisfaction and service quality are directly related to each other. The main purpose of the paper is to understand the relationship among service quality and tourist satisfaction in tourism industry. Satisfaction of customer primarily concerned with the quality of services provided by the suppliers. The paper is based majorly on secondary data collected from different published research articles, book chapters, reports etc. This paper also highlights the management strategies in tourism industry with future implication to enrich the experience of tourists.

Keywords: *Service Quality, Tourist Satisfaction, Tourist destination, Revisit, Customers*

Introduction

Service is an integral part in any activities of industry. Lovelock (2001) in his study described service as *“an act or performance offered by one party to another”*. Service Quality from a customer perspective is considered as a significant factor in deciding the satisfaction and success of tourism service providers. Many researchers argue that service quality and tourist satisfaction become an essential dimension for the growth of service providers. Service quality can have positive impact on tourist satisfaction that can increase revenue in the tourism industry.

Definition of Service

Quinn et al. (1987), stated service as an *“all financial activities where there is a concurrently utilization and manufacture of services and the center of attention is not on substantial production”*.

According to **Gronroos (1990)**, *“services are varied in nature where both the provider and customers have a noteworthy consequence on the service deliverance and production”*.

Review of Literature

Definitions of Service Quality

Parasuraman et al. (1985) described service quality as *“the degree and direction of discrepancy between customer’s perceptions and expectations”*.

According to **Bitner et al. (1994)** service quality is defined as the *“perceptions of the consumers towards the services rendered by service providers as compared to others”*.

Measurement of service quality: SERVQUAL scale

The SERVQUAL instrument was designed to measure service quality across a range of businesses. Parasuraman *et al.* (1985; 1988) measured the quality of services provided by the following:

- retail banks,
- a long-distance telephone company,
- a securities broker,
- an appliance repair and maintenance firm, and
- credit card companies

Perceived service quality and customer satisfaction

The concept of perceived quality was initiated by Heung *et al.* (2000) and they explained “the gap between expectations and perceptions of customers”. In contrast to the traditional tendency to equate the two constructs, the notion that perceived service quality and customer satisfaction are distinctive constructs has subsequently achieved some degree of consensus among researchers.

Hansemark and Albinsson (2004) defined “*satisfaction is an overall customer attitude towards a service provider, or an emotional reaction to the difference between what customers anticipate and what they receive, regarding the fulfillment of some need, goal or desire*”.

Customer Satisfaction

Theoretically, there are many investigations in the concept of customer satisfaction. Oliver (1989) differentiates the meaning of satisfaction from other researchers.

Although, researchers now generally agree regarding the distinctiveness and definitions of perceived service quality and satisfaction, their causal relationship is yet to be resolved. Over the time period with the viewpoint of researchers, there are two new methods of satisfaction:

“Transactional and Overall satisfaction”. Transactional Satisfaction refers to an idea about any purchase related event whereas overall satisfaction refers to the hoarded knowledge exhibited the actual customer’s gathering simulation for that particular products and services. The feeling of dissatisfaction comes when quality of services less than expectation. Usually when the quality of services meets with the expectation, customer is satisfied. Customer is delighted if expectation exceeds Kotler et al. (1996).

Gundersen et al. (1996) defined “*Customer satisfaction as a post consumption evaluative judgment concerning a specific product or service*”.

Kotler (2012) defined customer satisfaction “*as the level of one's feelings after comparing perceived performance or results compared with expectations*”.

Williams & Buswell (2003) research study shown that satisfaction of customers is the result of service received by the customers which is equals or exceeds their expectation. So, it is clear that customer satisfaction equal to perception and perception equal to expectation both are vice versa.

Tourist Satisfaction

Tourist satisfaction is described as “a collection of tourists’ attitudes about specific domains in the vacationing experience” (Pizam, Neumann, & Relchel, 1978, p. 317).

Chen and Tsai (2007) defined “*tourist satisfaction as a positive perception or feeling that tourists develop or acquire by engaging in recreational activities and is expressed as the degree of pleasure derived from such experiences*”.

Dmitrovic et al. (2009) confirmed that the higher tourist satisfaction can lead to higher profit and revenue for service providers. Customer satisfaction plays an important role and is a major factor in determining the level of tourist loyalty.

Mukhles (2013) found that there is a direct consequence of tourist satisfaction on quality of services and precised the judgment of travelers on the service quality at historical attraction of Petra.

SERVQUAL dimension

Table 1 SERVQUAL dimension

Dimensions	Definitions
Tangibility	The character of the external of the firm: physical facilities, equipment, and appearance of personnel
Reliability	The ability of the firm to perform the service as promised dependably and accurately
Responsiveness	This dimension examines the willingness of the employee to entertain and help the customer and provide a prompt service toward the customer
Assurance	Knowledge and the courtesy of the employees and their ability to inspire trust and confidence
Empathy	Caring to the customer and the firm can give individualized attention to their customers

Source: Yusof et al. (2014)

Research Methodology:

This research is a based on majorly secondary data collected from different published research articles, book chapters, government policies, reports, tourism policies and websites . The researcher also used the information and facts already available as base in order to analyze, explore and evaluate the problem at hand critically to figure out conclusion.

Conclusion and Future Implication

This paper highlights the relationship among tourist satisfaction and service quality in tourism industry. If we take into account that tourists when selecting a destination for their visit and stay experience, it is crucial from service provider to invest in service quality to enhance the experience of tourists for their satisfaction and visiting a place again.

The scope and significance of this study become vital for the tourism policy makers and tour planners for making the destination more attractive for enriching tourist experience in terms of tourist satisfaction and visitors to plan the visit to destination again.

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